

Sustainable polymer-tribology:
Developing novel multiscale thermoplastic
composites using recycled
high-performance fibers

Alejandra Marcela Ventura Cervellón

Mechanical Engineering, master's level (120 credits)
2021

Luleå University of Technology
Department of Engineering Sciences and Mathematics

Declaration

I hereby declare that except where specific reference is made to the work of others, the contents of this thesis are original and have not been submitted in whole or in part for consideration for any other degree or qualification in this, or any other university. This thesis is my own work and contains nothing which is the outcome of work done in collaboration with others, except as specified in the text and Acknowledgements.

Alejandra Ventura
August 2021

Acknowledgements

This master thesis project has been carried out at the Biotribology and Polymer Composites group in the Division of Machine Elements at Luleå University of Technology as part of the Erasmus Mundus TRIBOS+ Joint European Master's Programme.

I would like to thank everyone associated with the programme for allowing me to take part of this life changing experience. I sincerely wish to thank all the people who helped me along the way. Special thanks to my supervisor Prof. Nazanin Emami, who guided, empowered and inspired me through this journey. I am grateful to Lucas Kneissl, Stephanie Nunes and Hari Vadivel for all the productive discussions and guidance during the investigation. Many thanks to the staff in Tribolab and Materials Science Laboratory, Luleå University of Technology for their kind assistance.

Finally, I would like to thank my family and friends for their love and support, they have been a key part of this journey.

Abstract

The transition to a Circular Economy scheme that enables a more efficient usage of the resources is one of the most pressing needs in our society. From the industrial perspective this has been translated into new design philosophies and the search for more efficient systems. Polymeric composites have played a key role in the development of lighter components with good mechanical and tribological properties. Specifically, the demand of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymers (CFRP) has had an increasing trend since 1970s-1980s, becoming one of the kind of composites with the highest demand in the market to supply industries such as aerospace, automotive, construction, renewable energies, among others. With the increasing demand of CFRP materials some of the main challenges that arise are their disposal, environmental impact and cost of production to maintain the required supply. The use of Carbon Fibers as a reinforcement for polymeric matrices has been widely documented over the last decades, however the characterization of recycled Carbon Fibers for tribological applications is still scarce. Therefore, this investigation is focused on the mechanical and tribological characterization under water lubricated conditions of Ultra High Molecular Weight Polyethylene (UHMWPE) composites reinforced with virgin and recycled Carbon Fibers and Graphene Oxide. The findings of this work provide an important panorama regarding the performance of recycled Carbon Fibers, showing that they can have a comparable performance in mechanical properties and tribological behavior. This enables the use of recycled Carbon Fibers without compromising performance while reducing the environmental impact and cost.

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Nomenclature

Acronyms

<i>CAGR</i>	Compound Annual Growth Rate
<i>CF</i>	Carbon Fibers
<i>CFRP</i>	Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymers
<i>COF</i>	Coefficient of Friction
<i>DCM</i>	Direct Compression Molding
<i>DSC</i>	Differential Scanning Calorimetry
<i>EDS</i>	Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy
<i>EoL</i>	End of Life
<i>GO</i>	Graphene Oxide
<i>HDPE</i>	High Density Polyethylene
<i>LDPE</i>	Low Density Polyethylene
<i>LVDT</i>	Linear Variable Differential Transformer
<i>MoS₂</i>	Molybdenum disulfide
<i>MWCNT</i>	Multi-walled Carbon Nanotubes
<i>PA6</i>	Polyamide-6
<i>PA</i>	Polyamide
<i>PAI</i>	Polyamide-imide
<i>PE</i>	Polyethylene
<i>PEEK</i>	Polyether ether ketone

Nomenclature

<i>PEI</i>	Polyethylenimine
<i>PI</i>	Polyimide
<i>POM</i>	Polyoxymethylene
<i>PPS</i>	Polyphenylene sulfide
<i>PTFE</i>	Polytetrafluoroethylene
<i>rCF</i>	Recycled Carbon Fibers
<i>SEM</i>	Scanning Electron Microscopy
<i>UHMWPE</i>	Ultra High Molecular Weight Polyethylene
<i>vCF</i>	Virgin Carbon Fibers

Greek Symbols

λ	Mass fraction of reinforcement
μ	Coefficient of Friction

Roman Symbols

ΔH_m	Enthalpy of fusion [J/g]
X_c	Degree of crystallinity [%]

Chapter 1

Introduction

The search for lighter materials that can replace the traditional use of metals and can provide good performance of the components in a system has been one of the most important design challenges that engineering has faced in the last decades. This change in the design philosophy is leveraged by the improvement of efficiency in a system, which in turn has a simultaneous effect on costs and environmental impact.

The automotive industry is a good example that reflects this transition in the use of different materials. In the search for more efficient fuel consumption, the selection of materials for different components has leaned strongly towards polymers. Another example can be found in tribological applications that generate approximately 23% of the world's total energy consumption and from that 20% is used to overcome friction, while 3% is used to re-manufacture worn parts. In order to reduce friction and wear in tribological applications several actions can be taken, such as the use of lubricants, proper component design and an adequate selection of the materials [1].

When it comes to the lubricant selection, water based lubrication has gained relevance due to its advantages for applications where leakage of the lubricant can be harmful to the environment such as marine, hydropower applications, medical and food industries [2]. Some of the main advantages of using water as a lubricant are that it is largely available, doesn't have a flash point and has great cooling properties due to its specific heat capacity. However, its low viscosity becomes a challenge leaving the systems operating in a boundary lubrication regime where the selection of materials must be made carefully [3].

In the selection of materials, polymers are widely recognized for their light weight and versatility of applications, however they have certain limitations regarding their mechanical properties and operating temperatures, which is why the use of reinforcements to improve their performance has gained popularity, enabling their use in a wider range of applications.

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Polymeric composite materials can be reinforced with a variety of different fillers such as glass fibers, natural fibers, aramid fibers, carbon fibers, among others. However, Carbon Fibers (CF) are one of the most used reinforcements due to their high tensile strength, high elastic modulus, low thermal expansion coefficient and their ability to improve tribological performance [4].

Addressing the manufacturing of polymeric composites from a sustainable perspective with an approach that is directed to a circular economy, the challenge of the use of recycled materials becomes relevant. Therefore, the use of recycled carbon fibers as a reinforcement has taken a leading role in the last years [5].

1.1 Sustainability

According to the latest Grand View Research report, the composites market was estimated at USD 89.04 billion in 2019 and a Compounded Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 7.6% was reported as the forecast from 2020 to 2027. The growth in demand is strongly driven by the trend in searching for lighter materials for different industrial applications in the automotive, wind energy, aerospace, defense fields, among others. The demand of composites in the United States in 2017 represented USD 12.31 billion, as shown in Figure 1.1 [6].

Figure 1.1 U.S. Composites market size 2016-2027 [6].

Polymeric composite materials have found great acceptance in a variety of applications over the past decades, such as personal armor, food machinery, orthopedic implants, bearings and general manufacturing and their study has become increasingly interesting in the search for systems that are not only lighter but also more efficient.

The aircraft industry is a good example with the Boeing 787 and Airbus A350 having up to 50% of their weight in CFRP (Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymers) [7]. This has been a gradual process in the industry that took a transition from full metal-based structures in

the early 1920s-1930s to the start of the use of Carbon Fiber reinforced composites in the 1970s-1980s in some components that nowadays has been translated in a reduction of 25% of fuel consumption [8].

The demand of composite materials has been studied thoroughly [9–11] and it has an increasing trend, but among the different kinds of reinforcements the Natural Fiber Reinforced Products (11.68%), Carbon Fiber Reinforced Products (10.5%) and Glass Fiber Reinforced Products (6.6%) are the ones that exhibit the highest CAGR [9]. Just in Europe, a production of around 1,141 million tons of composite materials for Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymer was recorded in 2018 [10]. Also, it has been found that the opportunity in the UK by the growth of the composite materials market towards 2030 has an accumulated potential of £12.48 billion in different industries such as automotive, aerospace, defence, construction, oil & gas and renewable energies [11].

With an increasing demand of composite materials, some of the most important issues are the life cycle of the materials produced, waste disposal, their environmental impact, the energy consumed in their production and material cost [12]. Even if CFRP provide great advantages, their increasing use also generates an increasing amount of waste. Common sources of waste are out-of-date pre-pegs, manufacturing cut-offs, testing materials, production tools and end-of-life (EoL) components that have reached the end of its useful life and are not longer marketed, supported or sold by vendors. Nowadays, most of the CFRP waste is landfilled or incinerated but these solutions are highly unsatisfactory due to their environmental impact and cost [13].

The previous studies show a sustained growth over time for materials reinforced with Carbon Fibers, which is why it becomes necessary to rethink the supply sources of these fibers in a sustainable way, therefore the use of recycled fibers as reinforcement becomes relevant and has been leveraged by more strict environmental regulations that encourage a market for recycled fibers [10], some of those environmental regulations are:

- *End-of-Life Vehicles Directive 2000/53/EC* [14] that determine how to recycle, reuse, and recover parts from vehicles retired from use, how to limit waste and improve the environmental protection. In this document was established that from 1 January 2015 on a minimum of 95% of materials of end-of-life vehicles should be recovered and that at least 85% of the average mass of a vehicle be available for reuse and recycling.
- *Waste Framework Directive 2008/98/EC* [15] goes through the basic definitions regarding waste management, emphasizes the need for recycling, highlights the reduced availability of landfills and establishes the waste hierarchy (prevention, re-use, repurpose, recycling, recovery, disposal).
- *Directive (EU) 2018/849 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2018 amending Directives 2000/53/EC on end-of-life vehicles, 2006/66/EC on batteries and accumulators and waste batteries and accumulators, and 2012/19/EU on*

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Figure 1.2 Closed life cycle for Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymers (CFRP) [12].

waste electrical and electronic equipment (Text with EEA relevance) [16] address the objectives of new rules and set out how to change national laws in order to implement the directives and to implement the circular economy scheme.

- *Directive (EU) 2018/850 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2018 amending Directive 1999/31/EC on the landfill of waste (Text with EEA relevance)* [17] establish as mandatory to reduce by 2035 the amount of municipal waste to 10% of its total volume and to put in place a working quality control system and a waste disposal monitoring ability.

The formulation of the different legislation is highly focused on increasing the responsibility of the producers, increase recycling rates and reduce waste to landfill [18]. The production cost of Carbon Fibers has been reported for virgin (20-40 £/kg) and recycled (11-16 £/kg) fibers, the latter having a cost of just 40% of the virgin material [12].

The use of recycled fibers becomes appealing, not only because of the significant economic savings that this can represent in a large scale, but also because of the benefit of having a circular economy scheme that is sustainable in the long term and that meets the required demand due to the accelerated growth of the use of composite materials in different applications.

Perry et al. [19] has made a multi-circular proposal on the life cycle of CF, where the use of recycled fibers in different industries would depend on their demands and risk. This

hierarchical model proposes the fibers to go from more demanding applications (i.e. aircraft industry, automotive) to less demanding environments (i.e. sporting goods, civil construction) to guarantee that the fibers can find different markets across their life cycle without compromising quality or performance required for specific applications as exemplified in Figure 1.2.

1.2 Polymeric composites

Polymeric composites are physical mixtures of a polymer that acts as the matrix and a reinforcing filler that is the dispersed phase and whose function is focused on improving the properties of the material, e.g. the mechanical properties such as modulus or resistance to abrasion [20]. To meet the requirements of diverse end uses, polymers can be modified using materials with different properties as fillers and reinforcements; depending on the type of dispersed phase in a composite they can be classified as: particle reinforced, fiber reinforced and structural composites [21]. Fiber-reinforced materials have gained relevance in a short period of time, generating a wide space for the improvement of existing polymers instead of focusing in the expensive synthesis of new polymers [22].

One of the two main constituents within a fiber-reinforced composite is the matrix that acts as a binder for the fibers and that it is also responsible for the load transfer to the fibers. In other words, one of the main functions of the matrix is to keep the fibers in place, transferring stresses between the fibers, providing protection against adverse environments like chemicals or humidity, and protecting the fibers from mechanical degradation [23].

Care must be taken in the processing of composite materials, since the techniques and parameters used will have a direct impact on the interfacial strength of the material and consequently in the mechanical properties and performance depending on the interaction between the fiber and the matrix; that is why nano fillers that allow a greater contact area usually result in a stronger composite, due to an increased fiber surface-matrix interface [24]. For this reason, one of the options to improve the interaction at the interface between the fibers and the matrix, is the use of coupling agents, which are compounds with a low molecular weight that promote better adhesion between the fibers and the matrix [25]. Other alternatives include the physical and chemical treatment of the fibers to modify their behavior and improve their capacity to bond more efficiently with the matrix.

1.2.1 Polymeric composites in tribology

Tribology is the science and technology focused on the study of wear, friction and lubrication of moving parts in different mechanisms. It finds applications from daily life tasks to the systems used in all kinds of industries. The motivation behind the study of tribology came

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first from the economical impact that wear failures had in the British industry in the middle of the last century and since then the field has expanded by exploring different improvements in material selection, surface texturing, coatings, formulation of lubricants, among others [1, 26].

In tribological applications it is required that the materials can be capable of performing for long periods of time and very often in adverse conditions such as high temperatures, corrosive environments, mechanical and electrical stresses. The use of polymeric composites in tribological applications has generated special interest due to their low density, wear resistance, corrosion and impact resistance and the self-lubricity behavior that certain materials can present and even enhance when combined with functional fillers and reinforcements; consequently some of the most important materials in this field have been fiber-reinforced polymer composites [27–29]. Some of the most common materials used in tribological applications, their maximum service temperature and different fillers are presented in Table 1.1.

Table 1.1 Types of polymers and additives for tribocomposites (adapted from [27]).

Polymers - Thermoplastics		Additives	
Polymer	Max. Service temperature [°C]	Reinforcement	Friction and wear reducing
PE (HMWPE, UHMWPE)	80	Glass fiber	Graphite
POM	125	Carbon fiber	Graphite fluoride
PA (PA6, PA66, PA11)	130	Aramid fiber	Molybdenum disulfide
PEEK	150	Graphite fiber	Metal oxides
PPS	200	Boron fiber	Silicon fluids
PTFE	275	Asbestos fiber	
Polyesters	150-200	Polyesters	
Polyoxabenzates	300	Cotton	
Polyimides	200-300	Mica	
PAI	230		
PEI	200		

Reinforcing a polymer with fillers in the form of particulates and fibers will usually improve its stiffness and strength, but it will also have an influence on the wear resistance depending on the interaction of the fillers with the matrix and their particular properties. A specific filler will show its own wear mode and wear rate, however when combining different phases or fillers the effect on the overall performance of the composite will be a function of the contribution and interaction of all the phases. [30, 31]

1.2.2 Ultra-High Molecular Weight Polyethylene

Polyethylene (PE) is a polymer based on a simple molecular monomer structure made of carbon and hydrogen atoms. PE exists in different forms such as Low Density Polyethylene (LDPE), High Density Polyethylene (HDPE) and Ultra High Molecular Weight Polyethylene

1.2 Polymeric composites

(UHMWPE), each of them having their particular density, branching degree and mechanical properties [32].

UHMWPE is characterized by its extremely long chains with a molecular mass between $2 \times 10^6 - 6 \times 10^6 \text{ gmol}^{-1}$ and is able to form crystalline phases due to decreased sterical hindrance as a result of low branching; owing to its structure the loads can be efficiently transferred to the polymer backbone. UHMWPE is categorized as a semi crystalline thermoplastic polymer and in Friedrich's [33] pyramidal overview shown in Figure 1.3 it is listed as an Engineering Polymer.

This class of materials is characterized by having good chemical resistance, being used in a wide range of applications and having good load bearing capacity and wear resistance. It has been used as artificial acetabular cup in total artificial hip joints since the early 1960s [34], but also has applications in aerospace and automobile industries, food and beverage machinery, personal armor, recreational and general manufacturing [35].

Figure 1.3 Polymer classification based on cost, performance and formability (adapted from [33]).

In cyclic sliding conditions the material experiences plastic deformation in the bulk, having the point of maximum shear stress below the surface. It is at this point of maximum stress where the crack initiation will take place and eventually lead to the formation of flakes, causing wear in the macro scale [32].

Due to the increasing relevance of finding environmentally friendly solutions, water lubrication has become one of the most prominent options for ocean environments and hydro-power applications and polymeric materials have been found to perform well for such applications [36–38]. The wear mechanisms of UHMWPE in aqueous medium initiate in a microscopic scale where the contact between the asperities of the two surfaces induces

plastic deformations. The accumulation of plastic strain eventually leads the surface material to reach a critical strain that results in failure and the generation of wear particles [39].

1.3 Carbon based reinforcements

Carbon is an element with the ability to form multiple bonds and it's able to form a variety of different molecular arrangements. Among the different kinds of fillers and reinforcements that can be used with polymeric composites materials, carbon based fillers such as Carbon Fibers, Graphite, Graphene Oxide, Multi-walled Carbon Nanotubes (MWCNT) have been investigated [32, 40–42] and it was found that they can improve different properties depending on their own structure and interaction with the matrix. In this section, the two carbon based reinforcements considered for this investigation are described: Carbon Fibers and Graphene Oxide.

1.3.1 Carbon Fibers

Carbon Fibers (CF) are one of the most popular reinforcements for the formulation of composites due to their good mechanical properties and have been used widely in different applications in the last three decades in the aeronautical and automotive industry. Because of their structure these fibers have high stiffness, high tensile strength, low weight, good chemical resistance, low thermal expansion, and high temperature tolerance. Using CF as reinforcement for polymeric matrices has shown to improve wear resistance by carrying the main load between the surfaces and protecting the matrix from abrasion [43].

Carbon Fibers are mostly composed of carbon atoms with a blend of amorphous carbon and graphitic carbon. Their high tensile modulus comes from the graphitic form in which the atoms are arranged in a crystallographic structure of parallel planes or layers as shown in Figure 1.4. Strong covalent bonds exist between the carbon atoms in each plane, but the interaction between the planes is due to van der Waals forces that are weaker. These interactions result in highly anisotropic physical and mechanical properties for the carbon fibers. [23].

Extensive work has been conducted in the study of Carbon Fibers as a reinforcement and they show to have different effects in the tribological behavior depending on the concentration of the fibers and matrix used. Li et al. [30] found that the concentration of Carbon Fibers has a varying impact on the Coefficient of Friction (COF) and wear where the best performance was obtained at 20% concentration, but then leading to detrimental effects when increasing the loading of CF (10%wt, 20%wt and 30%wt) and using a Polyimide (PI) matrix under dry sliding conditions. Panin et al. [44] studied the effect of different sizes of CF in the tribological performance, ranging from the nano scale up to 2 mm length and showing

Figure 1.4 Graphite crystal structure [23].

that coefficient of friction and mechanical properties can vary depending on the size of the reinforcement and its interaction with the UHMWPE matrix, while the wear rates were improved for all the reinforced materials. Golchin et al. [45] used a PPS matrix and 15% CF content, finding a reduction in both friction coefficient and wear rates under water lubricated conditions.

However, the investigation of the effects in the tribological performance when using recycled carbon fibers is still limited and arises as a relevant field of study. Lin et al. [46] investigated the tribological behavior of polymeric composites using PEEK as a matrix with 10% of virgin and recycled Carbon Fibers of 6 mm in length under dry sliding conditions with different ratios of load and speed, finding that the recycled fibers exhibited good friction and wear properties, especially under moderate and severe Pressure/Velocity conditions. Ahsan et al. [47] compared the tribological behavior of recycled Carbon Fibers as received and after cryogenic treatment in epoxy composites under different loads, in dry sliding conditions and with 10% concentration of fibers; it was found that the treated fibers had a better interfacial bonding with the matrix leading to an improved performance regarding mechanical and tribological behavior.

Due to the increased use of CF in different fields, their disposal after their useful life is one of the challenges faced by the industries that end up disposing them in landfill sites. However due to the environmental impact, lack of compliance of regulations and the cost of landfill and incineration techniques, the recovery of CF from composites materials has been attempted with different methods such as chemical, mechanical, and thermal processes [48].

It has been found that the recycling process doesn't damage the surface of the fibers and that they can retain their initial properties such as modulus and ultimate tensile strength

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around 81% or more and still perform in a comparable scale to the virgin fibers [49]. The recycled CF offer a good solution in terms of cost and performance since they can be used as fillers in the synthesis of new composites to improve their mechanical, tribological and chemical properties and have a cost around 40% of the virgin material [4, 12].

1.3.2 Graphene Oxide

Graphene is a carbon allotrope and was first isolated in 2004. It has a two-dimensional structure of sp^2 bonded carbon atoms that provides extraordinary mechanical properties to the material, such as good strength and stiffness as well as good thermal and electrical conductivity [50]. Graphene Oxide (GO) has the same 2D structure with functional oxygen groups, such as epoxy and hydroxyl groups on its basal planes and carboxyl and ketone groups at its edges that makes it easier to disperse into polar solvents and form intercalated structures with polar molecules through the strong interaction with its functional groups [51].

Figure 1.5 Graphene and Graphene Oxide structures [52].

When used as a reinforcement, one of the greatest advantages of GO is that the high specific surface area and its two dimensional structure allows for a good interfacial adhesion which permits a good stress transfer between the matrix and the fillers. Tai et al. [53] found that the use of 3wt% of GO in a UHMWPE matrix can influence positively the wear resistance of the composites under dry conditions, improving it by up to 50% by changing the wear mechanism from delamination to abrasive wear and forming a transfer film on the counter surface.

Pang et al. [44] worked with dry, sea water and deionized water conditions, evaluating the behavior of UHMWPE composites reinforced with GO in different concentrations (0.1wt%, 0.5wt% and 1.0wt%). It was found that the incorporation of GO reduced the wear rates at all concentrations but the best performance was obtained at the highest loading and

for sea water lubricated conditions due to the good corrosion resistance of the composite and the lubricating effect of sea water. Previous studies on GO as a reinforcement have shown that it can increase the coefficient of friction, but that it can improve the wear resistance significantly. It has been found that it has good bio-compatibility when used with UHMWPE and its lower surface energy than the surface tension of water makes it an interesting candidate for water lubricated conditions. [54, 55]

1.4 Research gap and objectives

Extensive work has been conducted in the last decades to improve different properties of polymers (mechanical, electrical, tribological, etc.) with the use of reinforcements, depending on the requirements for each application. For example, high end applications such as aerospace, automotive and energy generation industries demand most of the time the highest mechanical properties that can be achieved in a material.

Carbon based reinforcements have gained relevance due to their good mechanical properties, however their production has increased significantly among different industries, generating large quantities of waste.

The challenges of recycling processes and systems have begun to be studied, identifying the collection, separation and classification systems, as well as the need for commercialization routes as some of the most important issues to solve in order to successfully recycle composites and find a market for the recycled materials.

The study and understanding of the performance of recycled Carbon Fibers is still limited while mainly only focusing in the mechanical characterization of the materials. This investigation focuses on the search of solutions that can contribute towards a sustainable engineering that can comprise not just the mechanical design aspect, but can also have an economical and environmental effect.

The aim of this master thesis is to experimentally determine if the use of recycled Carbon Fibers (rCF) gives comparable mechanical properties and tribological performance to those obtained with UHMWPE composites using virgin fibers (vCF) under water lubricated conditions.

The objectives of this work are:

- To study the effect of virgin and recycled Carbon Fibers at different loading of reinforcement on the mechanical properties (Hardness, Young Modulus and Ultimate strength) of UHMWPE composites.
- Evaluation of frictional and wear behaviour of the composites.

Introduction

- Manufacture of multiscale thermoplastic composites using recycled Carbon Fibers (rCF) and Graphene Oxide (GO) to study their interaction and influence on the further improvement of the tribological behavior of the composites.
- To evaluate the ratios between cost and performance (mechanical and tribological) in the development of composites using virgin and recycled reinforcements.

Chapter 2

Methodology

In this chapter the materials, experimental procedures to manufacture the composites and characterization techniques used in this investigation are described.

2.1 Materials

The following specifications presented for each material were obtained from the technical data sheets provided by each manufacturer.

- *MIPELON™ UHMWPE XM-220 (Mitsui Chemicals, Japan)* was used as the matrix polymer to manufacture the composites. The UHMWPE particles had an average size of $30\ \mu\text{m}$, a molecular weight of $2 \times 10^6\ \text{g/mol}$ and a powder density of $0.4\ \text{g/cm}^3$. [56]
- The virgin carbon fibers (Tenax®-A HT M100 100mu) were obtained from *Toho Tenax America Inc* with an average length of $100\ \mu\text{m}$, diameter of $7\ \mu\text{m}$, tensile strength of 4.28 GPa, elongation at break of 1.9%, Young Modulus of 225 GPa and bulk density of $1.82\ \text{g/cm}^3$. [57]
- The recycled carbon fibers (CF.LS MLD100) were provided by *PROCOTEX, S.A. CORPORATION, France* and have an average size of $100\ \mu\text{m}$, diameter of $7\ \mu\text{m}$, tensile strength of 3.5 GPa, elongation at break of 1.5%, Young Modulus of 230 GPa, metal contamination of less than 0.5 g/1000 g and bulk density of $1.7\ \text{g/cm}^3$. [58]
- The Graphene Oxide nanosheets were obtained from *NanoInnova Technologies, Spain* and had a monolayer thickness of 0.7 – 1.2 nm and an average lateral dimension of 3 – 7 μm . [59]

2.2 Composite processing

The work in this thesis comprises the manufacturing process of different composites using UHMWPE as a matrix and virgin and recycled Carbon Fibers as a reinforcement. The Carbon Fibers are added in three different weight percentages of 10 wt%, 20 wt% and 30 wt%. Subsequently, the incorporation of Graphene Oxide into the composite containing an optimized amount of Carbon Fibers is studied in order to investigate a possible improvement in the tribological behavior of the composites. The manufacturing process for both cases is illustrated in Figure 2.1.

The manufacturing process of the composites with the Carbon Fibers included two steps:

1. Dry ball milling of CF with UHMWPE
2. Direct Compression Molding (DCM) of the composite

The processing of the composites with Graphene Oxide and Carbon Fibers was carried out in five stages:

1. Ultrasonication of Graphene Oxide in ethanol
2. Wet ball milling of GO with UHMWPE
3. Removal of excess ethanol
4. Dry ball milling adding the Carbon Fibers
5. Direct Compression Molding (DCM) of the composite

The weight percentages for the fillers were determined based on the previous research made with Carbon Fibers (CF) and Graphene Oxide (GO) [43, 4, 60, 38]. The detail of all the composites prepared for this investigation is presented in Table 2.1.

2.2.1 Ultrasonication

To manufacture the composites *10vCF 3GO* and *10rCF 3GO* shown in Table 2.1 that include the incorporation of Graphene Oxide, the exfoliation of the nano reinforcement was done in 20ml of ethanol, using a Model 3000MP ultrasonic disperser from *BioLogics Inc., USA* with a titanium tip at 50Hz for 60 minutes.

The implementation of ultrasonication helps to break down agglomerates of the GO particles in order to guarantee a homogeneous solution prior to the mixing process with the polymer.

Figure 2.1 Composite's manufacturing process

2.2.2 Ball Milling

The ball milling process was carried out differently depending on the composite being manufactured and the reinforcement used. The parameters were taken from previous research done in order to optimize the mixing process [61, 62, 41]. A schematic representation of the ball milling configuration is shown in Figure 2.2.

Dry Ball Milling

The mixing process of the Carbon Fibers was conducted with a dry ball milling technique using a PM100 planetary mill from *Retsch, Germany* for 5 minutes at 100 rpm with 250 Zirconia balls of 5 mm diameter.

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Table 2.1 Manufactured composites

Sample	Reinforcement (wt%)		
	Virgin Carbon Fibers (vCF)	Recycled Carbon Fibers (rCF)	Graphene Oxide (GO)
UHMWPE	-	-	-
10vCF	10	-	-
20vCF	20	-	-
30vCF	30	-	-
10vCF 3GO	10	-	3
10rCF	-	10	-
20rCF	-	20	-
30rCF	-	30	-
10rCF 3GO	-	10	3

Figure 2.2 Schematic diagram of planetary ball mill

Wet Ball Milling

For the composites containing Graphene Oxide, prior to the addition of the Carbon Fibers a wet milling step was implemented. The mixing process of GO with UHMWPE was done under wet conditions using the 20ml of ethanol in which the particles were exfoliated and using a PM100 planetary mill from *Retsch, Germany* for 120 minutes at 200 rpm with 500 Zirconia balls of 5 mm diameter.

2.2.3 Drying

The drying process was an intermediate step used between the wet ball milling with GO and the dry ball milling used to mix the carbon fibers as it was carried out in an universal oven *UF75, Memmert, Germany*.

After the wet ball milling, the slurry obtained was partially dried by transferring it between two beakers inside the fume hood in order to separate the materials from the zirconia balls. Once the material was separated from the zirconia balls, it was placed in the oven at 60 °C for 24 hours to fully evaporate the remaining ethanol in the powder.

2.2.4 Direct Compression Molding

After having obtained the final compositions in powder form, a compression molding process was carried out to shape the samples. The equipment used in this process was a *Fontijne Presses LP 300, Netherlands* hot-press and a 60 mm x 60 mm x 5 mm mold was used to produce the samples.

Before the compression molding process, the mold was cleaned to remove any residue of previous processes. The powder necessary to fill the mold was approximately 18.6 g to complete each pressing step. In order to avoid adhesion of the composite to the mold, 0.05 mm thick brass foil was used to cover the surfaces. The compression molding process was performed at 190 °C for 70 minutes, with several short pressing cycles of 105 kN.

2.3 Characterization

In this section, the methods and experimental procedures for the characterization of the manufactured composites are described.

2.3.1 Differential Scanning Calorimetry

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) was used to determine the degree of crystallinity of the composites. The measurements were carried out in a *DSC821* from *Mettler Toledo, Germany* under an inert nitrogen atmosphere with a flow rate of 80 ml/min. The samples used for each experiment weighed approximately 10 mg and three experiments were performed for each composite. The reported values are the average of the three measurements. The method used to characterize the composites consisted of four steps:

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1. 25 °C - 160 °C at 10 °C/min rate
2. 160 °C, isothermal for 10 minutes
3. 160 °C - 25 °C at 10 °C/min rate
4. 25 °C - 450 °C at 10 °C/min rate

The initial heating and cooling process comprising steps 1 to 3 was performed to erase any thermal history in the material and step 4 was the one from which the enthalpy values were taken to calculate the crystallinity of each composite using equation 2.1 from [63]:

$$X_c(\%) = \frac{\Delta H_m}{(1 - \lambda)\Delta H_m^0} \cdot 100 \quad (2.1)$$

where ΔH_m is the measured enthalpy of fusion of the samples, ΔH_m^0 is the enthalpy value of melting of the 100% crystalline form of UHMWPE (289 J/g) [64] and λ is the mass fraction of reinforcement in the composite.

2.3.2 Microhardness

For microhardness measurements the equipment used was a *Matsuzawa MXT- α* , Japan tester, using the Vickers method and applying a load of 25 gF for 35 seconds, performing 15 measurements in each of the nine samples. The dimensions of the samples used were 35 mm x 25 mm x 4 mm. The measurements were performed following the standard ASTM E384-17 *Standard Test Method for Microindentation Hardness of Materials*.

2.3.3 Tensile test

To obtain the mechanical properties of the composites such as Young Modulus and Ultimate Tensile Strength, a tensile test was performed following the guidelines from the standard ASTM D638-14 *Standard Test Method for Tensile Properties of Plastics* and using a sample specimen Type IV. The standard dimensions for this kind of sample are: Length overall (115 mm), Width overall (19 mm), Thickness (4 mm), Gage length (25 mm) and Width of narrow section (6 mm).

The equipment used to perform the tests was an *ElectroPuls E10000*, Instron, USA and the loading rate used for the tests was 5 mm/min as indicated in the standard. An extensometer was used in the first stage of the measurements to obtain the strain data in the linear elastic region of the materials. The sequence of the method used to perform the measurements was carried out as follows:

1. Loading: strain from 0% to 0.35%
2. Unloading: strain from 0.35% to 0%
3. Removing the extensometer
4. Loading at 5mm/min until reaching the Ultimate Tensile Strength of the material

The first two steps of the method are focused on loading the material in its elastic region to calculate the Young Modulus. The second loading cycle was done without tracing the strain but loading the material until its Ultimate Tensile Strength or failure. For each composite a total of four samples were tested.

2.3.4 Wettability

To determine the wettability of the composites, contact angle measurements were performed using an *Attension Theta, Biolin Scientific, Sweden*. Performing the sessile drop method using 3 μL of distilled water that were deposited on the surface of the samples for each measurement.

The contact angle developed on the surface was measured after one second and a total of ten measurements were performed on each sample. Figure 2.3 shows part of the distribution of drops in one sample to determine the contact angle between the distilled water and the sample surface.

Figure 2.3 Contact angle measurements.

Table 2.2 Pin on disc parameters

Pin on Disc parameters		
Time	24	<i>h</i>
Load	88.72	<i>N</i>
Velocity	0.13	<i>m/s</i>
Sliding distance	11.27	<i>km</i>
Area of pin	16.4	<i>mm²</i>

2.3.5 Pin on disc

The tribological characterization to obtain the friction and wear data was carried out in a tribometer *TE67 Pin-on-Disc Tribometer, Phoenix Tribology, UK*. The countersurface used for all the tests were Inconel 625 discs with a roughness of $0.2 \mu\text{m}$. The roughness conditions were selected to increase the interaction of the surfaces during sliding, allowing to characterize the materials in boundary/mixed lubrication regimes and the desired roughness was obtained through polishing and sandpaper grinding using a method described by Vadivel [41].

The 3D optical surface profiler *Zygo NewView™ 7300, USA* was used to obtain topographic measurements of Inconel discs which were used as a countersurface in the pin on disc experiments. These measurements were performed in order to guarantee the roughness values ($Ra = 0.2 \mu\text{m}$) of the surface before setting up each experiment.

Before placing any specimen in the Pin on Disc machine, a calibration procedure was done in order to get consistent results across all the tests. The parameters used for each test are presented in Table 2.2.

For each kind of composite, four tests were run under water lubricated conditions using distilled water. In the machine set up a Linear Variable Differential Transformer (LVDT) sensor was used to record the vertical displacement of the sample and be able to later determine the wear rate for each test. Figure 2.4 shows the detailed set up of the free weights and the LVDT sensor positioning to run a test.

2.3.6 Scanning Electron Microscopy / Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy

For the observation of the surfaces of interest, a high resolution bench-top Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) *JCM - 6000 Neoscope, Jeol, Japan* was used in different stages of the investigation:

Figure 2.4 Tribometer set up.

- To examine possible differences between the virgin and recycled fibers and to evaluate their composition by means of Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS) technique
- To study the dispersion of the reinforcements in the UHMWPE matrix in the powder form
- To examine the surfaces of the material and behavior of the fibers after their failure in the tensile test
- To examine the surfaces of the material and behavior of the fibers after being broken in a brittle fracture using liquid nitrogen
- To study the surface of the worn pins used in the tribological test and to identify the wear mechanisms
- To study the Inconel 625 discs used in the tribological test and the wear tracks resulting after each test

The equipment was operated using High Vacuum, using the Secondary Electrons mode with a Standard probe current and an accelerating voltage of 15kV.

The preparation of polymeric samples needed to be done by sputtering with a thin Platinum layer of 15nm of thickness in order to make their surface conductive and allow the observation of the samples. Without this prior treatment the samples can not be observed under the SEM due to its working principle of the beam of electrons interacting with the surface of the material.

The sputtering procedure was done in a *High Vacuum Sputter Coater, Leica EM ACE600, USA*.

Chapter 3

Results and discussions

This chapter displays the results obtained from the different measurements and analysis performed for this investigation with main focus on the mechanical and tribological performance of the composites.

3.1 Morphology

The integrity and morphology of the Carbon Fibers was examined under the Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) in order to verify their length distribution and investigate the differences between the virgin and recycled carbon fibers. In conformity with the data sheets provided by the manufacturers, the virgin and recycled fibers are declared to be $100 \mu m$ length, however the measured batches of fibers exhibited a mean length of $124.1 \pm 62.0 \mu m$ for the Virgin fibers and a length of $114.9 \pm 62.7 \mu m$ for the recycled fibers, having a difference of $9.2 \mu m$ between their average values.

It was found from the close observation of the virgin fibers showed in Figure 3.1a at x350 magnification, that some of them had irregular ends identified by the red squares in the figure, as consequence of the fracture of the fibers into smaller portions that have a shorter length than the average.

The recycled fibers at x350 magnification are presented in Figure 3.1b, where it can be observed how some of the fibers have defects on their surface showing a more flattened shape and having marks in the middle across their length. It is inferred that those marks are a result of the handling and recycling process that the fibers go through.

The observation of the fibers and EDS measurements before any processing was important to establish their initial state, however no other visible features were identified on

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the virgin or recycled Carbon Fibers that could suggest chemical contamination from the recycling process or the presence of any sizing on their surface.

The integrity of the length and good dispersion of the virgin and recycled fibers was checked after the ball milling processing and the observation of the formulations with 10% rCF and 30% rCF is showed in Figure 3.2. The measurements reported a mean length of $115.8 \pm 45.4 \mu\text{m}$ after 5 minutes of ball milling without degrading or damaging the fibers during the process.

Figure 3.1 SEM micrograph of Carbon Fibers using x350 magnification, electron backscatter diffraction and acceleration voltage of 20kV. The red squares denote in (a) the irregular surface on the ends of the fibers and in (b) the features found along the length of the recycled fibers.

Figure 3.2 SEM micrograph of UHMWPE and Recycled Carbon Fibers with (a) 10% rCF and (b) 30% rCF concentrations after ball milling for 5 minutes at x350 magnification.

The formulation of the samples with the different concentrations of Carbon Fibers and Graphene Oxide that are presented in Table 2.1 were chosen in order to study the effect of different loadings of the short Carbon Fibers, the concentrations were selected using as a reference the previous research that has been done using mostly virgin Carbon Fibers and different polymeric matrices [4, 38, 43, 60].

The addition of Graphene Oxide to the 10% CF formulation was done in order to explore and characterize the effect of the nano-size filler and the possible improvement on the performance and properties of the composite, but with special interest on the possible improvement on the specific wear rates. It has been previously reported by Tai et al. [53] that by adding 3% GO to a UHMWPE matrix an improvement of 50% on the wear rate could be obtained. While Pang et al. [44] found a consistent improvement on the wear rates of UHMWPE composites with GO in different concentrations (0.1%, 0.5% and 1%) in dry, deionized water and seawater conditions.

3.2 Crystallinity

Crystallinity as a measure of the arrangement of the chains in a semi-crystalline polymer is inversely proportional to the amorphous regions in the material. A high degree of crystallinity is a quantitative description of the structure in a polymer in the micro scale that is directly linked to the physical and mechanical properties that a material can exhibit on the macro scale.

The effect of reinforcements in a polymeric matrix and its degree of crystallinity can be diverse depending on the type of filler and its concentration, they can act favourably serving as a nucleation sites and improving the crystallization process or they can hinder the crystallization process by acting as obstacles in the arrangement of the chains in the polymer [41, 63, 65–67].

It can be seen in Figure 3.3 that the crystallinity for the different composites reinforced with Carbon Fibers did not vary significantly from the crystallinity of the pure UHMWPE (53.93%). And among the different formulations, no statistically significant difference was found between the virgin and recycled Carbon Fibers composites as shown in Figure A.1.

Within the narrow range of variation in crystallinity for the composites, when increasing the amount of fibers from 10% to 30%, a decreasing trend in the crystallinity can be observed as a consequence of the higher amount of fibers and their agglomeration that starts to lower the mobility of the polymeric chains as observed by Liang et al. [65]. Their investigation was focused on the study of PA6/CF composites in three different concentrations (10%, 15% and 20%), finding that the CF play a role as a nucleation agent in the PA6 matrix and that the addition of a rigid filler as the fibers can restrict the chain mobility of polymer molecules and

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Figure 3.3 Crystallinity of UHMWPE based composites with different concentrations of virgin and recycled Carbon Fibers and Graphene Oxide. UHMWPE is used as the reference baseline to compare with the composites using Carbon Fibers.

this affects the crystallinity degree of the composites. It was found that by increasing the cooling rate, the composites exhibited a decrease in crystallinity.

However, in this study even at the highest concentration of carbon fibers the crystallinity degree remains very similar to the one exhibited by the pure material, not finding any statistical evidence of a negative impact in the overall crystallinity levels of the composites. Therefore, it can be claimed that there's no evidence of a difference between the crystallinity of the composites with virgin and recycled Carbon Fibers. Contrary to the findings of Zheng et al. [66] that found that short CF acted as nucleation agents in SCF/PEN composites, improving the crystallization process and accelerating the crystallization rate. Similar results were also found by Batista et al. [67] where the best properties for PPS/CF composites were identified when using lower cooling rates, finding evidence of fiber/interface improvement and crystallites nucleation on the fiber reinforcement surface.

The samples including 10% *wt* of Carbon Fibers and 3% *wt* of Graphene Oxide didn't show a significant improvement in the crystallinity degree compared to the samples using

just the Carbon Fibers. This trend has been observed in previous work [41, 32] where the addition of GO in smaller concentrations (0.5% and 1%) showed to just slightly modified the crystallinity of the composites. Similar results have been reported by Jain et al. [43], where the addition of CF (10%) and GO (0.5%) to a PPS matrix lead to a decrease in the crystallinity of the composites. By adding a higher amount of GO (3%) no significant changes were found, even if the combined effect of the fillers in different scales in the nano and micro size together was expected to generate an improved organization of the polymeric chains that might lead to an increase in crystallinity.

It must be noted that in the processing of the composites the cooling rate was not controlled and it was given just by natural convection. However, it is known that the cooling rate has an influence on the crystallization process [65, 67] and this can be a factor that could be controlled and measured in order generate an improvement on the crystallinity degree of the composites.

3.3 Microhardness

The results of the measurements of hardness in each composite are presented in Figure 3.4, where it can be observed how by increasing the CF loading the hardness of the composites also increases, this trend is consistent with the reinforcing function of the Carbon Fibers.

For the composites manufactured in this investigation, the hardness values were improved from 3.95 HV for pure UHMWPE up to 7.82 HV and 9.71 HV for the samples reinforced with 30% virgin and recycled Carbon Fibers correspondingly; this represents an improvement of 98% and 146% compared with the pure polymer, showing an important increase in hardness.

From the results obtained, it can be observed how the composites reinforced with the recycled fibers exhibit higher values of hardness to the ones obtained with the virgin fibers. This difference in the hardness of the composites is related to the difference in properties of the fibers where the recycled fibers exhibit a lower elongation at break (1.5% vs. 1.9%) that is relative measure of toughness and that is inversely proportional to hardness. Simultaneously, the recycled fibers also have a higher Young Modulus (230 GPa vs. 225 GPa) than the virgin fibers [57, 58]. This influence of the fibers is more notorious when increasing their concentration up to 20% and 30% and where the difference in hardness between virgin and recycled fibers becomes 2.01 and 1.89 HV correspondingly.

Increased hardness with the addition of CF has been reported in several studies. Wang et al. [68] found that by adding CF (28-56 μm in length) in different concentrations (5%, 10%, 15% and 20%) in a UHMWPE matrix the hardness was improved up to 10% from 67 for pure UHMWPE in Shore scale up to 74 for the composites with 20% CF. Jain et al. [43] obtained an increase of 7%, 15% and 19% in hardness for a PPS matrix when adding 10%,

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Figure 3.4 Vickers Hardness of polymeric composites reinforced with virgin and recycled Carbon Fibers in different concentrations. Neat UHMWPE is used for comparison on the reinforcement effect of the CF.

20% and 30% of virgin Carbon Fibers. While Vadivel et al. [38] reported an improvement of 7% in hardness of UHMWPE based composites reinforced with 10% virgin Carbon Fibers.

For the three formulations with just Carbon Fibers (10%, 20% and 30%) the statistical analysis of the measurements showed in Figure A.2 found that there is evidence of a difference between the behavior of the samples. It can be claimed that the hardness of the composites was not just improved with the addition of Carbon Fibers when compared against pure UHMWPE, but also the recycled fibers provided the composites with a better performance regarding hardness to the one obtained with the virgin fibers.

However, an interesting behavior can be observed when incorporating Graphene Oxide to the composites where combined with the virgin Carbon Fibers the nano-size reinforcement improved the hardness of the composite, but when added with the recycled fibers the overall hardness of the composite was slightly decreased, narrowing the gap between both composites. This was also evident on the statistical analysis, where no significant statistical difference was found just for the formulation with 10% CF + 3% GO as showed in Figure A.2b. This

provides evidence about the different effects that Graphene Oxide can have with the virgin or recycled Carbon Fibers.

3.4 Tensile test

The tensile mechanical properties of UHMWPE and its composites with Carbon Fibers were measured performing tensile test and are displayed in Figure 3.5 and Figure 3.6. The general trend of the increase in Young's Modulus and Ultimate Tensile Strength with the increase of Carbon Fiber loading is typical and as expected from those reported in several studies [48, 69, 70] with Carbon Fibers.

This behavior shows the quality of a good interface and the ability to transfer the load from the matrix to the fibers successfully. The higher the amount of Carbon Fibers reinforcing the matrix, the better the tensile properties of the composites since there is more fibers that are able to withstand the applied load [71].

From the results obtained in this investigation, a consistent behavior was obtained, improving Young's Modulus with the successive addition of Carbon Fibers from 1.09 GPa for the pure UHMWPE up to 3.83 GPa and 3.36 GPa for the composites with 30% concentration of virgin and recycled Carbon Fibers respectively, having an improvement of 251% and 208% for such composites. Additionally, the improvement in Ultimate Tensile Strength of the composites was reported to be 98% for the virgin and 105% for the recycled fibers for the same concentration of 30% CF when compared to the pure UHMWPE matrix. Increasing the ultimate tensile strength values up to 39.65 MPa and 41.13 MPa for the virgin and recycled fibers respectively.

Similar results were found by McNally et al. [48] who investigated the reinforcement effect of recycled Carbon Fibers of 250 μm in length on a PE matrix using different concentrations (0, 1, 3, 5, 8, 10, 15, 20, 25, and 30 *wt%*). Their results reported an increase in Young's Modulus from 258 MPa for PE alone to 724 MPa for the composite with 30 *wt%* CF, representing an increase of 180%. The ultimate tensile strength was improved by 28%, going from 17.5 MPa for PE to 22.3 MPa for the composite with 30% CF.

When analyzing the lower concentrations of CF, the 10% vCF composites had an increase of 44% and 66% in Ultimate Tensile Strength and Young's Modulus correspondingly. The influence of adding Graphene Oxide to the 10% CF composites didn't show a statistically significant improvement on the properties of the material, even if small changes on the mean values can be observed, the tensile properties didn't experience a significant enhancement as reported in Figure A.3 and Figure A.4.

Similarly, the comparison between the performance of virgin and recycled Carbon Fibers across the different concentrations did not show any statistically significant difference

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Figure 3.5 Variation in Young's Modulus as a function of CF loading in UHMWPE based composites.

between them. This allows to claim that the tensile mechanical properties of the composites is the same for virgin and recycled fibers.

Zhong et al. [69] found that the incorporation of 10% CF on a PEEK matrix lead to an increase of 48% and 154% in tensile strength and Young's Modulus respectively. While Lin et al. [46] worked on the comparison in performance of virgin and recycled Carbon Fibers of 6 mm in length, using a 10% concentration of fibers reinforcing a PEEK matrix. The virgin fibers exhibited a slightly better behavior than the recycled ones, reporting an improvement of 30% in Tensile Strength and 180% in Young's Modulus.

In Figure 3.7 the surfaces of the samples with 10%, 20% and 30% of recycled CF after the tensile test are presented in different magnifications. The areas highlighted with the red squares show evidence of the different interfacial adhesion features between the CF and UHMWPE matrix. The fibers remained well embedded in the matrix even after the fracture, showing the failure of the material due to the final rupture of the fibers. This indicates that the load transfer from the matrix to the fibers was performed optimally. The samples with 10% and 20% of recycled Carbon Fibers exhibit a good dispersion in the matrix, while the

Figure 3.6 Ultimate Tensile Strength of different polymeric composites reinforced with virgin and recycled Carbon Fibers and Graphene Oxide.

samples with a loading of 30% start to present evidence of agglomeration in different regions as the one indicated with the red square where three fibers are agglomerated in the same region.

In Figure 3.8 the behavior of the surfaces after the fracture during the tensile test for the composites with virgin Carbon Fibers is presented, the difference in morphology is more obvious when comparing the surfaces from the 10% vCF + 3% GO and the 20% vCF, the sample with just the fibers presents flattened areas instead of the flake-like appearance characteristic of the GO.

On the 20% sample is indicated the area where the breakage of the fibers is notorious, denoting a good transfer of the load and a good retention of the fibers in the matrix. Similar behavior as the one obtained with the recycled fibers in Figure 3.7 is observed for the 30% vCF formulation, where the agglomeration of the fibers starts to be evident finding some gaps in areas where the fibers are not absolutely surrounded by UHMWPE.

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Figure 3.7 SEM micrography of surfaces after tensile test (10%, 20% and 30% of recycled Carbon Fibers).

Figure 3.8 SEM micrography of surfaces after tensile test (10% vCF + 3% GO, 20% and 30% of virgin Carbon Fibers).

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Figure 3.9 SEM micrography of surfaces after tensile test (10% vCF + 3% GO and 10% rCF + 3% GO).

The addition of Graphene Oxide to the samples show a change in the overall morphology of the composites as depicted in Figure 3.9, showing a characteristic filamentous mesh structure combined with a flake-like appearance in specific areas as the one highlighted in the 10% vCF + 3% GO sample in Figure 3.9 and comparable to the same morphology found by Pang et al. [54] when adding up to 1% of GO.

The described behavior was checked also with the implementation of cryogenic fracture using liquid nitrogen (Appendix B). The consistency found between the fractures of the samples using virgin and recycled fibers is evident. In Figure B.1 and Figure B.3 the fractured surfaces for the 10% and 20% CF concentrations are presented and the dispersion of the fibers across the matrix is satisfactory without excessive pull-out fibers. Figure B.2 with the addition of 3% GO exhibits a very different morphology as it has been observed in the surfaces after tensile test, but keeping the integrity in dispersion of the fibers and a good interface fiber/matrix. While in Figure B.4 the samples with 30% exhibit the same evidence of good adhesion to the matrix but with some fibers experiencing agglomeration.

The highest values for Young's Modulus and Ultimate Tensile Strength were obtained for the 30% CF formulations, however those are also the samples that exhibit the larger variations in standard deviation, showing a wider range for the values obtained. This provides evidence on how the reinforcement effect at the highest loading of fibers starts to vary more due to the different features between samples. A more consistent behavior was found for the 10% and 20% CF composites.

3.5 Wettability

The wettability of the materials dictate the behavior that they have when interacting with a liquid phase depending on their surface free energy, the interaction with water is one of the important parameters affecting the tribological performance under water lubricated conditions. A hydrophobic nature can be translated in less affinity with water, allowing the surface of the material to slide easily in a water medium and reducing the water absorption into the material. While a hydrophilic behavior denotes affinity with water, allowing the water to spread on the surface and having a high surface energy and consequently a higher adhesion between the material surface and water [72].

These interactions were quantified with the measurement of the contact angle formed with water for all the studied composites and the results are presented in Figure 3.10. It can be observed how due to the hydrophobic nature of carbon, the addition of the Carbon Fibers contributed to increase the contact angle, reducing the wettability and moving towards a less hydrophilic behavior the measurements for the different composites when increasing the concentration of Carbon Fibers.

However, the measurements for pure UHMWPE show already a contact angle of 85.9°, that is very close to the barrier between hydrophobic/hydrophilic behavior that is defined at 90°[73]. For the samples containing just CF, a maximum increase of 10% in the contact angles was obtained for the samples with 30% of virgin Carbon Fibers, representing a statistical significant change in the wettability behavior of the material.

A more pronounced effect was found when incorporating Graphene Oxide to the 10% CF samples, where an increase of 33% and 32% in the contact angle was obtained with the use of virgin and recycled fibers respectively when compared to pure UHMWPE. This effect obtained from the use of GO can be associated to the particular production process utilized to obtain the GO nano sheets and how this enhance the hydrophobic nature of the carbon structure generating an impact on the performance of the composite.

The hydrophobicity of the material and its influence in the frictional and wear behavior has been investigated by different authors [74–77]. Golchin et al. [76] didn't find a correlation between wettability and wear behavior of different polymers. While Vadivel et al. [38] found

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Figure 3.10 Contact Angle values measured on UHMWPE based composites reinforced with Carbon Fibers and Graphene Oxide using $3 \mu L$ of distilled water.

that the increase in the contact angle of UHMWPE based composites reinforced with CF and GO had an influence in friction and wear.

However, Suñer et al. [77] found mixed effects when adding GO in different concentrations (0.1%, 0.3%, 0.5%, 0.7%, 1% and 2%) to a UHMWPE matrix, the lower concentrations showed a decrease on the contact angle and the higher concentrations of GO resulted on increased contact angles. Borutto et al. [75] studied the influence of wettability on friction and wear of different combination of materials and suggested that a combination of hydrophilic pin and hydrophobic disc provides the lowest friction and wear of the materials.

From the results displayed in Figure 3.10 and in contrast with the previous investigations, it can be seen that the effect of GO is prominent when combining it with the Carbon Fibers, generating a more hydrophobic behavior just as found by Suñer et al. [77]. Regarding the performance between the virgin and recycled fibers among each formulation, it was found that there's a statistically significant difference for the 20% and 30% samples with the virgin Carbon Fibers exhibiting an improved behavior. For the two formulations with 10% CF the

performance between the virgin and recycled fibers can be claimed that is the same as it can be seen in Figure A.7.

3.6 Tribological characterization

The tribological characterization was done under water lubricated conditions as described in section 2.3.5 and the results obtained for the Coefficient of Friction and wear rates are presented in Figure 3.11 and Figure 3.13.

3.6.1 Friction

The reported values of coefficient of friction in Figure 3.11 are the ones obtained when the steady state was achieved and without taking into account the run-in stage of the material where the contact has not stabilized. The frictional behavior of most of the samples was stable after 15 hours, therefore the last five hours of each test were taken into account to average the friction coefficient values.

With the incorporation of Carbon Fibers to the UHMWPE matrix a generalized reduction in the coefficient of friction can be appreciated for all the concentrations. However, the lowest COF obtained correspond to the samples with 10% CF, reporting values of $\mu = 0.039$ and $\mu = 0.037$ for the virgin and recycled fibers correspondingly. These values represent an improvement of 60% and 62% when compared against UHMWPE which reported a coefficient of friction of $\mu = 0.098$. Similar results have been reported by Golchin et al. [45] when reinforcing a PPS matrix with 15% of CF and reporting a reduction of 61% in Coefficient of Friction. Jain et al. [43] reported the same trend as well with a PPS matrix reinforced with 10% CF and obtaining an improvement of 44% compared to the pure material.

When increasing the amount of Carbon Fibers in the composites formulations up to 20% and 30%, an increasing trend in the COF values can be identified. The presence of more fibers protect the polymer integrity providing higher strength and stiffness as it was shown in Section 3.4, however it also causes to have more fibers rubbing against the counter surface, obtaining as an outcome an increase in the coefficient of friction.

The comparison in performance between virgin and recycled Carbon Fibers across the different concentrations is consistent with the previous results discussed in Section 3.3 regarding the higher hardness of the samples with recycled Carbon Fibers. A similar trend can be found between hardness and coefficient of friction results, where the difference between the properties of the samples with 10% CF concentration is not that pronounced but when increasing the amount of fibers to 20% and 30% the gap between the performance of virgin

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Figure 3.11 Coefficient of Friction of polymeric composites reinforced with virgin and recycled Carbon Fibers. The values reported correspond to the average values of the last five hours of 24h experiments, four samples were measured for each family of composites.

and recycled fibers becomes more evident. However, this difference in performance with the virgin and recycled fibers regarding the COF is not reported as statistically significant as it can be observed in Figure A.5. It can be claimed that in terms of friction both kind of fibers, virgin and recycled perform comparably.

Among the different formulations, it is congruent that by having harder composites the coefficient of friction obtained would be higher since the interaction of the fibers with the counter surface becomes more severe. However, even for the highest loading of Carbon Fibers with 30% content, a reduction of 33% in the Coefficient of Friction was obtained when compared to the pure UHMWPE where the adhesive component of friction gets enhanced causing high values of coefficient of friction [30]. Contrasting results have been obtained by Li et al. [30] where the lowest COF was obtained for the highest concentrations of fibers (20% and 30%) with the use of a PI matrix.

The addition of Graphene Oxide into the 10% CF samples didn't exhibit a significant influence in the coefficient of friction, the values remained unchanged for the samples with

3.6 Tribological characterization

and without GO. A similar behavior has been found by several authors [41, 43, 44, 55, 78] where the reported Coefficient of Friction for the composites using GO as a reinforcement didn't provide a significant change when compared to the pure matrices. According to the above, it can be expected that the addition of GO to the Carbon Fibers would not provide an improvement in the COF.

Figure 3.12 displays the relation between the Coefficient of Friction and the contact angle developed by the composites. A direct correlation can be observed between contact angle and COF. The slope of the samples with virgin CF is less steep than the one obtained with recycled CF; the increase in hydrophobicity is better when adding vCF and this translates to lower coefficient of friction than the ones obtained when using recycled fibers. In general terms, it can be observed how the lowest coefficient of friction was displayed by the composites with 10% of Carbon Fibers.

Figure 3.12 Friction Coefficient vs. Contact Angle.

The influence of Graphene Oxide in wettability can be clearly appreciated, being the samples with GO the only ones exhibiting a hydrophobic behavior with contact angles above 90°. Contrary to expected, even if the samples with GO exhibited an increase in

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hydrophobicity, this did not have an impact in the COF as it has been described as well by Golchin et al. [76].

3.6.2 Wear

The wear rates for each composite were calculated using the data obtained from the LVDT sensor. The calculation of the specific wear rates is done to report the wear volume per unit of load vs. the distance in each test. The values presented in Figure 3.13 are the average values of four measurements for each composite.

Figure 3.13 Wear rate.

The wear rate for pure UHMWPE was reported as $2.38 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$ and the best performance was exhibited by the composite with 10% of virgin Carbon Fibers, having a wear rate of $1.32 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$ that translates to a reduction of 45% compared to the pure material. The incorporation of GO in the samples didn't show a significant improvement for the virgin or recycled fibers. Even if the use of GO decreased the hardness of the composites, this didn't show to have an impact on the wear rates. Diverse results have been reported on

3.6 Tribological characterization

the effects of GO in the wear rates of composites [41, 43, 44, 53, 55, 78]. With the use of just GO as a reinforcement both effects have been observed, an increase on the wear rates of different composites using PI and PEEK as a matrix [55, 78] and a decrease or the same wear rates have been reported in UHMWPE and PPS matrices [41, 43, 44, 53]. However, on samples with the use of CF and GO Vadivel [3] reported an increase on the wear rates obtained when adding GO compared to the ones obtained with the use of just Carbon Fibers.

The variation in the wear rates across the different concentrations of Carbon Fibers had an increasing trend, however those variations remained within a narrow range from 1.32 to $1.73 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$ and all the composites exhibited an improved wear rate compared to pure UHMWPE.

When comparing the performance between virgin and recycled Carbon Fibers, it can be observed how the virgin fibers have lower wear rates for each formulation, being inversely proportional to the mechanical properties where the virgin fibers have higher values of Young's Modulus that can be translated into an influence to the improved wear rates. However those differences remain statistically insignificant as observed in Figure A.6, making the behavior of both virgin and recycled fibers completely comparable. Similar results have been obtained by [46] where the mechanical and tribological performance of virgin and recycled fibers (6 mm length) under dry sliding conditions in a PEEK matrix proved to have a comparable behavior. For this reason the images displayed for the analysis of pins and discs from Figure 3.14 to Figure 3.16 are the ones corresponding to the recycled fibers, finding the same behavior for the formulations with virgin fibers.

Figure 3.14 presents the pins of the samples with 10% and 30% recycled Carbon Fibers at x300 magnification after being tested, the red arrows indicate the sliding direction in each sample. It can be noted the difference in the concentrations of fibers in the same area for the two pins. Both samples present evidence of the fibers on the surface that are highlighted with red squares in the Figure, those fibers protect the polymeric matrix from severe abrasion by carrying the main load in the contact.

Figure 3.14 Worn pins after test (10% and 30% of recycled Carbon Fibers).

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In Figure 3.15 and Figure 3.16 the Inconel 625 discs used as countersurface for the tests with pure UHMWPE, 10% rCF, 10% rCF + 3% GO and 30% rCF are presented. It can be observed how the discs used with the 10% rCF and 10% rCF + 3% GO samples present evidence of a transfer layer on the surface. The pattern of the transfer layer is patched and not continuous over the entire wear track, however this is due to the water lubricated conditions that prevent the formation of a full and stable transfer layer. The presence of the transfer film and its composition was verified with EDS technique and the analysis of the discs used with the 10% rCF + 3% GO and 30% vCF samples can be appreciated in Appendix C. Figure C.3 and Figure C.4 present the atomic composition of areas with deposits with high concentrations of Carbon that correspond to the transferred material from the pins with 30% CF. Figure C.9 and Figure C.10 present the same behavior for the 10% rCF + 3% GO samples.

The disc used for the 30% rCF sample present some particles transferred to the countersurface but a cleaner surface can be observed where it's not just the effect of the water avoiding the formation of a full transfer film, but also the presence of more fibers rubbing against the surface that prevent the formation of a thicker film.

The evidence of the transfer film explains the reduction in coefficient of friction presented in the 10% Carbon Fiber content composites. Once the film is formed, it allows to have a smoother contact between the sliding surfaces. This doesn't seem to happen with the UHMWPE samples where the wear track doesn't present the same formation of a transferred film and this also explains the more severe contact between the surfaces and the higher coefficient of friction.

Figure 3.15 Countersurface disc after 24 h test (10% and 30% of recycled Carbon Fibers). The red arrows indicate the sliding direction. Images obtained using x300 magnification, secondary electron and acceleration voltage of 15kV.

From the study of Figure 3.14, Figure 3.15 and Figure 3.16 it can be concluded that the main wear mechanisms acting in the contact are abrasive and adhesive wear, the first one being the predominant one due to the water lubricated environment that prevents a total adhesion of the two surfaces. The abrasive wear pattern parallel to the sliding direction is

Figure 3.16 Countersurface disc after 24 h test (UHMWPE and 10% rCF + 3% GO). The red arrows indicate the sliding direction. Images obtained using (a) x330 and (b) x300 magnification, secondary electron and acceleration voltage of 10kV.

visible in both samples and evidence of the adhesive wear mechanism was found on the countersurfaces and the patched transfer film formed that can be appreciated in Figure 3.15 and Figure 3.16.

However, the incorporation of the Carbon Fibers as a reinforcement into the polymeric matrix provide an important protection to the material against abrasive wear reducing up to 45% the wear rate compared to the one reported for the pure UHMWPE. For water lubricated conditions similar results were reported by Dangsheng et al. [79] where with the addition of CF the wear rates were reduced significantly when compared with pure UHMWPE. In dry sliding conditions similar results have been provided by Li et al. [30] with the use of the same concentrations of CF (10%, 20% and 30%) in a PI matrix and by Lin et al. [46] with the comparison in performance of virgin and recycled fibers (6mm in length) where both proved to behave comparably as in this investigation.

3.7 Life Cycle Assessment of Carbon Fibers

The Life Cycle Assessment is one of the valuable tools for decision making, to get insights of the environmental impacts, saving opportunities and process implications of materials [80]. It has been reported that CFRP materials can provide weight savings up to 65% when compared to steel automotive parts [81] and up to 20% when compared to aluminum parts in the automotive industry [82].

However, in this study are considered just the costs of production and commercialization of virgin and recycled Carbon Fibers as displayed in Figure D.1. The average costs of the fibers in the market that have been used for calculations are the ones reported by Pimenta et

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al. [12]. While the energy consumption in the production of virgin Carbon Fibers and the process of pyrolysis to recycle the fibers are the ones reported by Amaechi et al. [5]. The demand of Carbon Fibers and the CAGR that were taken into account are the ones reported by the U.S. Commercial Service for the European market in March 2020 [83].

The scenario modelled in the calculations presented in Figure D.2 includes the volume of the demand reported for Carbon Fibers in 2018 as a baseline with an annual growth rate of 10.1%. The calculations are based in a scenario where the consumption of recycled Carbon Fibers reaches a 20% of the total value of the market.

It can be observed how the projection for 2022 if such proportion in consumption between virgin and recycled fibers (80/20) would be accomplished for a projected demand of 188,822 ton, the savings could represent $7.74E9$ MJ in energy and £623 MM when compared with the consumption of just virgin Carbon Fibers. In a projection of five years those savings become up to $4.74E10$ MJ in energy and £3,812 MM.

It is important to note how the calculations presented in Appendix D do not include the further savings that could be obtained when replacing a component that was previously made with a metal and transition directly to a rCF composite formulation.

The benefits of the use of recycled Carbon Fibers include several advantages from a performance perspective where the properties of the material can be the same as the ones obtained with virgin fibers, the cost is reduced by 55% and the energy consumption is reduced by 18% in a scheme where the 20% of the total demand of CF is supplied with recycled Carbon Fibers.

Chapter 4

Conclusion

In this investigation the manufacturing of eight different composites was performed in order to evaluate if the use of recycled Carbon Fibers and Graphene Oxide as a reinforcement can provide comparable results in mechanical properties and tribological behavior under water lubricated conditions to the one obtained with the use of virgin Carbon Fibers.

- The examination of the initial conditions of the virgin and recycled fibers revealed a difference of $9.2 \mu m$ in the measured mean length. In the recycled fibers it was found the presence of grooves across their length, causing a more flattened shape for the fibers with this defect that is presumed it is a result from the recycling process.
- The reinforcing action of the Carbon Fibers caused an improvement in the mechanical properties of the composites in all concentrations. The highest increase in mechanical properties was obtained for the samples with 30% recycled Carbon Fibers, reporting an improvement of +208% in Young's Modulus, +105% in Ultimate Tensile Strength and +146% in Hardness.
- The tribological performance of the composites was improved with the addition of Carbon Fibers in all concentrations when compared against pure UHMWPE. However, the composites that performed the best were the ones with 10% of Carbon Fibers, reporting the lowest Coefficient of Friction ($\mu_{10vCF} = 0.039$ and $\mu_{10rCF} = 0.037$) and lowest wear rates. The addition of Graphene Oxide didn't have an statistical significant impact to improve the wear resistance of the composites, providing an identical behavior to the one obtained with the samples containing just Carbon Fibers.
- The examination of the worn pins and discs after the tribological test revealed the presence of a transfer film in the countersurface for the samples with 10% CF and 10% CF + 3% GO, propitiating the reduction of -62% in Coefficient of Friction reported for those composites. The main wear mechanisms observed were adhesive and abrasive wear, the latter one being the predominant. The reduction of -45% in the wear rates

Conclusion

is attributable to the incorporation of Carbon Fibers in the polymer that protect the matrix from severe abrasion.

- The friction coefficient and wear rates are increased when increasing the concentration of CF in the composites, however all the composites demonstrate to have an improved behavior than the one exhibited by pure UHMWPE. The results from the mechanical and tribological characterization strongly proved that the performance of the recycled Carbon Fibers is comparable to the one obtained with virgin Carbon Fibers and this enables and encourage the use of recycled Carbon Fibers instead of the use of virgin ones in different applications and industries. The use of recycled Carbon Fibers aims to reduce the environmental impact in the manufacture of composites, to create economical savings and to contribute towards a circular economy scheme.
- The benefits of the use of recycled Carbon Fibers include several advantages, from a performance perspective the properties of the material can be the same as the ones obtained with virgin fibers, the cost is reduced by 55% and the energy consumption is reduced by 18%. In a scheme where the 20% of the total demand of CF for 2022 is supplied with recycled Carbon Fibers, this could represent savings up to $7.74E9$ MJ in energy and £623 MM in costs.

Chapter 5

Future work

Extensive work has been done in this investigation to characterize the mechanical and tribological behavior of virgin and recycled Carbon Fibers and the use of Graphene Oxide, however there are some areas that can be further explored in future work in a similar direction.

- The cooling rates used in the processing of composites can play an important role in the crystallization process. Therefore in order to investigate their impact and to possibly obtain an improved crystallinity on the composites, the control of the cooling rates after compression moulding could be done.
- The enhancement of the interface fiber/matrix can be done using chemical or thermal processes on the fibers. The use of binders agents in the formulation of the composites could improve the compatibility between the matrix and the reinforcement. Exploring the possible surface treatments on the fibers or addition of binders could result in an even stronger interface between fibers and matrix, having a direct impact on the properties of the composites.
- Different processing parameters or techniques could be explored in the manufacturing stage of the composites in order to obtain a better dispersion of the reinforcement and to address the agglomeration that was found when higher amounts of Carbon Fibers (30%) were used.
- The manufacturing of composites with recycled fibers of different sizes and recycled with different techniques could help to understand in more detail the effects of the recycling process in fibers with different dimensions.
- A more detail assessment on the Life Cycle of the fibers and their environmental impact compared with the production of Carbon Fibers could provide a deeper analysis on the environmental and economical aspects of the use of recycled fibers in large scales across different industries.

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Appendix A

Student's t-test statistical analysis

In order to compare statistically the performance of the polymeric composites reinforced with virgin, recycled Carbon Fibers and Graphene Oxide, the Student's t-test was performed to determine whether or not a significant difference between the results exists.

The t-test was performed for each pair of formulation of samples, comparing the results between the virgin and recycled Carbon Fibers for the seven characterization techniques used in this investigation.

The t-test was performed in each set of data assuming unequal variances, using a significance level of 0.05 ($\alpha = 0.05$) and taking into account the following hypothesis:

- H_0 : The performance of the recycled Carbon Fibers is the same as the performance of the virgin Carbon Fibers
- H_1 : The performance of the recycled Carbon Fibers is different as the performance of the virgin Carbon Fibers

The results for each t-test are presented from Figure A.1 to Figure A.7, highlighting in colors the t parameter calculated for each set of data and the critical two-tail parameter to accept or reject the null hypothesis.

As defined in the statistical analysis, when the calculated t parameter is higher than the critical two-tail value, the null hypothesis is then rejected, finding a statistical significant difference in the results. The results of the tests where a statistical significant difference was found are highlighted in yellow.

Student's t-test statistical analysis

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances		
<i>Crystallinity</i>	10 vCF	10 rCF
Mean	53.89081123	56.7704729
Variance	0.04047182	1.33862985
Observations	2	3
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	2	
t Stat	-4.216390673	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.025954304	
t Critical one-tail	2.91998558	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.051908608	
t Critical two-tail	4.30265273	

(a) 10% CF

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances		
<i>Crystallinity</i>	20 vCF	20 rCF
Mean	54.27768166	55.11534025
Variance	0.99409879	7.460424125
Observations	2	3
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	3	
t Stat	-0.48492884	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.33046575	
t Critical one-tail	2.353363435	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.6609315	
t Critical two-tail	3.182446305	

(c) 20% CF

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances		
<i>Crystallinity</i>	10vCF + 3GO	10rCF + 3GO
Mean	55.25394742	57.69399038
Variance	0.270694399	0.000790926
Observations	2	2
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	1	
t Stat	-6.622764158	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.047702645	
t Critical one-tail	6.313751515	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.09540529	
t Critical two-tail	12.70620474	

(b) 10% CF + 3% GO

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances		
<i>Crystallinity</i>	30 vCF	30 rCF
Mean	52.94611962	53.56401384
Variance	0.239460734	2.994798571
Observations	2	3
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	2	
t Stat	-0.584378053	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.309051156	
t Critical one-tail	2.91998558	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.618102313	
t Critical two-tail	4.30265273	

(d) 30% CF

Figure A.1 Student's t-test results for Crystallinity of composites reinforced with Carbon Fibers and Graphene Oxide.

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances		
Hardness	10 vCF	10 rCF
Mean	5.086666667	5.98
Variance	0.096952381	0.321714286
Observations	15	15
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	22	
t Stat	-5.347182126	
P(T<=t) one-tail	1.14123E-05	
t Critical one-tail	1.717144374	
P(T<=t) two-tail	2.28246E-05	
t Critical two-tail	2.073873068	

(a) 10% CF

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances		
Hardness	10vCF + 3GO	10rCF + 3GO
Mean	5.693333333	5.873333333
Variance	0.40352381	0.40352381
Observations	15	15
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	28	
t Stat	-0.776012209	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.222123773	
t Critical one-tail	1.701130934	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.444247547	
t Critical two-tail	2.048407142	

(b) 10% CF + 3% GO

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances		
Hardness	20 vCF	20 rCF
Mean	5.94	7.88
Variance	0.156857143	0.864571429
Observations	15	15
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	19	
t Stat	-7.434356082	
P(T<=t) one-tail	2.44664E-07	
t Critical one-tail	1.729132812	
P(T<=t) two-tail	4.89328E-07	
t Critical two-tail	2.093024054	

(c) 20% CF

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances		
Hardness	30 vCF	30 rCF
Mean	7.546666667	9.886666667
Variance	1.084095238	2.792666667
Observations	15	15
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	23	
t Stat	-4.602851062	
P(T<=t) one-tail	6.26247E-05	
t Critical one-tail	1.713871528	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.000125249	
t Critical two-tail	2.06865761	

(d) 30% CF

Figure A.2 Student's t-test results for Hardness of composites reinforced with Carbon Fibers and Graphene Oxide.

Student's t-test statistical analysis

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances		
<i>Modulus</i>	10 vCF	10 rCF
Mean	1.8125	1.6975
Variance	0.064958333	0.075825
Observations	4	4
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	6	
t Stat	0.612988341	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.281191628	
t Critical one-tail	1.943180281	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.562383256	
t Critical two-tail	2.446911851	

(a) 10% CF

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances		
<i>Modulus</i>	20 vCF	20 rCF
Mean	2.58	2.235
Variance	0.0199	0.0667
Observations	3	4
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	5	
t Stat	2.259766077	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.036686603	
t Critical one-tail	2.015048373	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.073373205	
t Critical two-tail	2.570581836	

(c) 20% CF

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances		
<i>Modulus</i>	10vCF + 3GO	10rCF + 3GO
Mean	1.97	1.785
Variance	0.024533333	0.057633333
Observations	4	4
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	5	
t Stat	1.29078494	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.126618554	
t Critical one-tail	2.015048373	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.253237108	
t Critical two-tail	2.570581836	

(b) 10% CF + 3% GO

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances		
<i>Modulus</i>	30 vCF	30 rCF
Mean	3.83	3.356666667
Variance	0.154333333	0.152033333
Observations	4	3
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	4	
t Stat	1.584294613	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.094150939	
t Critical one-tail	2.131846786	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.188301877	
t Critical two-tail	2.776445105	

(d) 30% CF

Figure A.3 Student's t-test results for Young's Modulus of composites reinforced with Carbon Fibers and Graphene Oxide.

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances		
Strength	10 vCF	10 rCF
Mean	28.75427597	27.06457373
Variance	0.414029294	1.652799172
Observations	4	4
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	4	
t Stat	2.350649942	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.039229812	
t Critical one-tail	2.131846786	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.078459623	
t Critical two-tail	2.776445105	

(a) 10% CF

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances		
Strength	10vCF + 3GO	10rCF + 3GO
Mean	27.23782416	29.39024072
Variance	0.625993123	0.095839064
Observations	4	4
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	4	
t Stat	-5.066851751	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.003573076	
t Critical one-tail	2.131846786	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.007146152	
t Critical two-tail	2.776445105	

(b) 10% CF + 3% GO

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances		
Strength	20 vCF	20 rCF
Mean	31.69438215	30.93434327
Variance	0.129852587	18.11553489
Observations	3	4
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	3	
t Stat	0.355446896	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.372888915	
t Critical one-tail	2.353363435	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.74577783	
t Critical two-tail	3.182446305	

(c) 20% CF

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances		
Strength	30 vCF	30 rCF
Mean	39.65492188	41.12942127
Variance	15.57596734	43.09281835
Observations	4	3
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	3	
t Stat	-0.345076074	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.37640709	
t Critical one-tail	2.353363435	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.75281418	
t Critical two-tail	3.182446305	

(d) 30% CF

Figure A.4 Student's t-test results for Ultimate Tensile Strength of composites reinforced with Carbon Fibers and Graphene Oxide.

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances		
<i>Wear</i>	<i>10 vCF</i>	<i>10 rCF</i>
Mean	1.319767746	1.618109002
Variance	0.032283362	0.198252327
Observations	3	4
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	4	
t Stat	-1.214695769	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.145641416	
t Critical one-tail	2.131846786	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.291282832	
t Critical two-tail	2.776445105	

(a) 10% CF

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances		
<i>Wear</i>	<i>10vCF + 3GO</i>	<i>10rCF + 3GO</i>
Mean	1.384142849	1.366330321
Variance	0.075171803	0.12186905
Observations	4	4
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	6	
t Stat	0.080255985	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.469321819	
t Critical one-tail	1.943180281	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.938643637	
t Critical two-tail	2.446911851	

(b) 10% CF + 3% GO

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances		
<i>Wear</i>	<i>20 vCF</i>	<i>20 rCF</i>
Mean	1.465777095	1.577717183
Variance	0.105248	0.133472524
Observations	4	4
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	6	
t Stat	-0.458216538	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.331461957	
t Critical one-tail	1.943180281	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.662923915	
t Critical two-tail	2.446911851	

(c) 20% CF

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances		
<i>Wear</i>	<i>30 vCF</i>	<i>30 rCF</i>
Mean	1.578283786	1.733394121
Variance	0.088945347	0.222844567
Observations	4	4
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	5	
t Stat	-0.55557117	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.3012223	
t Critical one-tail	2.015048373	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.6024446	
t Critical two-tail	2.570581836	

(d) 30% CF

Figure A.6 Student's t-test results for Specific Wear Rate of composites reinforced with Carbon Fibers and Graphene Oxide.

Student's t-test statistical analysis

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances		
<i>C Angle</i>	10 vCF	10 rCF
Mean	79.865	83.38875
Variance	11.67011667	16.35966964
Observations	10	8
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	14	
t Stat	-1.966162115	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.03471529	
t Critical one-tail	1.761310136	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.069430579	
t Critical two-tail	2.144786688	

(a) 10% CF

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances		
<i>C Angle</i>	20 vCF	20 rCF
Mean	92.703	85.5375
Variance	9.821023333	38.79696429
Observations	10	8
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	10	
t Stat	2.96720848	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.007056517	
t Critical one-tail	1.812461123	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.014113035	
t Critical two-tail	2.228138852	

(c) 20% CF

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances		
<i>C Angle</i>	10vCF + 3GO	10rCF + 3GO
Mean	114.0975	113.5488889
Variance	28.45159286	20.48763611
Observations	8	9
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	14	
t Stat	0.22715593	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.411793044	
t Critical one-tail	1.761310136	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.823586088	
t Critical two-tail	2.144786688	

(b) 10% CF + 3% GO

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances		
<i>C Angle</i>	30 vCF	30 rCF
Mean	95.292	87.67
Variance	27.15712889	28.77931429
Observations	10	8
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	15	
t Stat	3.033518693	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.004190216	
t Critical one-tail	1.753050356	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.008380432	
t Critical two-tail	2.131449546	

(d) 30% CF

Figure A.7 Student's t-test results for Contact Angle of composites reinforced with Carbon Fibers and Graphene Oxide.

Appendix B

Cryogenic fracture using liquid nitrogen

The cryogenic fracture using nitrogen was performed in the different samples to examine the quality of the dispersion of the fibers and to observe in detail the behavior of the interface fiber/matrix.

Figure B.1 SEM micrography of surfaces after cryogenic fracture (10% vCF and 10% rCF).

Cryogenic fracture using liquid nitrogen

Figure B.2 SEM micrography of surfaces after cryogenic fracture (10% vCF + 3% GO and 10% rCF + 3% GO).

Figure B.3 SEM micrography of surfaces after cryogenic fracture (20% vCF and 20% rCF).

Cryogenic fracture using liquid nitrogen

Figure B.4 SEM micrography of surfaces after cryogenic fracture (30% vCF and 30% rCF).

Appendix C

Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) of countersurfaces

C.1 Disc used with 30% vCF sample

Figure C.1 Electron image for EDS analysis of Inconel 625 disc used as countersurface with 30% vCF sample under water lubricated conditions.

Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) of countersurfaces

Figure C.2 EDS analysis: atomic count of elements present in Spectrum 12 of Figure C.1.

Figure C.3 EDS analysis: atomic count of elements present in Spectrum 13 of Figure C.1.

C.1 Disc used with 30% vCF sample

Figure C.4 EDS analysis: atomic count of elements present in Spectrum 14 of Figure C.1.

Figure C.5 EDS analysis: atomic count of elements present in Spectrum 15 of Figure C.1.

Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) of countersurfaces

Figure C.6 EDS analysis: atomic count of elements present in Spectrum 16 of Figure C.1.

C.2 Disc used with 10% rCF + 3% GO sample

Figure C.7 Electron image for EDS analysis of Inconel 625 disc used as countersurface with 10% vCF + 3% GO sample under water lubricated conditions.

Figure C.8 EDS analysis: atomic count of elements present in Spectrum 1 of Figure C.7.

Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) of countersurfaces

Figure C.9 EDS analysis: atomic count of elements present in Spectrum 2 of Figure C.7.

Figure C.10 EDS analysis: atomic count of elements present in Spectrum 3 of Figure C.7.

C.2 Disc used with 10% rCF + 3% GO sample

Figure C.11 EDS analysis: atomic count of elements present in Spectrum 4 of Figure C.7.

Figure C.12 EDS analysis: atomic count of elements present in Spectrum 5 of Figure C.7.

Appendix D

Life Cycle Assessment calculations

The Life Cycle Assessment calculations were performed in order to estimate the impact and benefits that a transition to a higher usage of recycled Carbon Fibers could be translated considering the demand in Europe.

CAGR	10.10%	
Production vCF	230	MJ/kg
Pyrolysis recycling	25	MJ/kg
GHG vCF	27.7	kg CO2/kg
Cost vCF	30	£/kg
Cost rCF	13.5	£/kg

Figure D.1 Parameters used for Life Cycle Assessment calculations for virgin and recycled Carbon Fibers.

Life Cycle Assessment calculations

	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026
Volume [k ton]	129	141	156	172	189	208	229	252	277
Volume [ton]	128500	141478.5	155767.829	171500.379	188821.917	207892.931	228890.117	252008.019	277460.829
Volume [kg]	1.29E+08	1.41E+08	1.56E+08	1.72E+08	1.89E+08	2.08E+08	2.29E+08	2.52E+08	2.77E+08
Virgin									
Energy	2.96E+10	3.25E+10	3.58E+10	3.94E+10	4.34E+10	4.78E+10	5.26E+10	5.80E+10	6.38E+10
Cost	3.86E+09	4.24E+09	4.67E+09	5.15E+09	5.66E+09	6.24E+09	6.87E+09	7.56E+09	8.32E+09
Recycled									
Energy	3.21E+09	3.54E+09	3.89E+09	4.29E+09	4.72E+09	5.20E+09	5.72E+09	6.30E+09	6.94E+09
Cost	1.73E+09	1.91E+09	2.10E+09	2.32E+09	2.55E+09	2.81E+09	3.09E+09	3.40E+09	3.75E+09
v/r (80/20) - Energy									
Virgin	2.36E+10	2.60E+10	2.87E+10	3.16E+10	3.47E+10	3.83E+10	4.21E+10	4.64E+10	5.11E+10
Recycled	6.43E+08	7.07E+08	7.79E+08	8.58E+08	9.44E+08	1.04E+09	1.14E+09	1.26E+09	1.39E+09
Sum [MJ]	2.43E+10	2.67E+10	2.94E+10	3.24E+10	3.57E+10	3.93E+10	4.33E+10	4.76E+10	5.24E+10
Savings [MJ]	5.27E+09	5.80E+09	6.39E+09	7.03E+09	7.74E+09	8.52E+09	9.38E+09	1.03E+10	1.14E+10
v/r (80/20) - Cost									
Virgin	3.08E+09	3.40E+09	3.74E+09	4.12E+09	4.53E+09	4.99E+09	5.49E+09	6.05E+09	6.66E+09
Recycled	3.47E+08	3.82E+08	4.21E+08	4.63E+08	5.10E+08	5.61E+08	6.18E+08	6.80E+08	7.49E+08
Sum [£]	3.43E+09	3.78E+09	4.16E+09	4.58E+09	5.04E+09	5.55E+09	6.11E+09	6.73E+09	7.41E+09
Savings [£]	4.24E+08	4.67E+08	5.14E+08	5.66E+08	6.23E+08	6.86E+08	7.55E+08	8.32E+08	9.16E+08

Figure D.2 Life Cycle Assessment calculations for virgin and recycled Carbon Fibers.